

LEVEL OF SATISFACTION AND OUTCOME IN PATIENTS PRESENTING TO THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, KARACHI

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Abstract

Background: Emergency departments play a critical role in healthcare delivery. This is particularly so in low-resource settings where timely and coordinated care can be challenging. Patient satisfaction serves as a vital measure of care quality in these high-pressure environments. This study examined the level of satisfaction among patients visiting the emergency department of a tertiary care hospital in Karachi and also explored factors associated with their reported experiences.

Methods: We conducted a cross-sectional survey involving 189 patients who received care in the emergency department of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center, Karachi from 2nd March 2025 to 2 June 2025. Trained data collectors administered a structured questionnaire that captured demographic information, clinical outcomes, and self-reported satisfaction. We used chi-square tests to evaluate associations between satisfaction and patient characteristics, including age, gender, education, income, residence, and outcome of care.

Results: Most participants (78.8%) reported being satisfied with the care they received. Satisfaction levels did not vary significantly across demographic groups. However, patients who were admitted to inpatient wards or referred to other facilities expressed higher satisfaction compared to those who were discharged home ($p = 0.01$). Although trends suggested greater satisfaction among rural residents and individuals with higher education, these differences were not statistically significant.

Conclusions: Patient satisfaction in the emergency department appeared closely linked to the perceived continuity and outcome of care. Demographic factors played a lesser role. Improving discharge communication, enhancing provider-patient interaction, and addressing patient expectations may contribute to better satisfaction outcomes. These findings highlight the value of prioritizing patient-centered practices in emergency care. Particularly in tertiary hospitals serving diverse urban populations.

INTRODUCTION

Patient satisfaction is widely recognized as a key measure of the quality of care delivered in emergency departments (EDs).¹ Patient satisfaction may not accurately reflect the technical quality of care provided, as it is more closely linked to the patient's overall perception of the care experience.² This perception often influences whether patients choose the same emergency department for future visits or recommend it to others.³ Emergency departments are often seen as a representation of the overall healthcare system, as they typically serve as the initial point of contact between patients and medical services. With a rising number of patient visits, these units are facing increasing pressure, often outpacing the availability of doctors, support staff, and medical resources.^{4,5}

Patient satisfaction reflects the extent to which individuals feel their needs and expectations have been met during medical care. It serves as an indicator of the alignment between the care patients anticipate and the care they believe they have received.⁶ Patient satisfaction is typically assessed through surveys administered to patients or their family members.⁷ The majority of studies evaluating patient satisfaction have examined a range of service-related factors—such as perceived and actual waiting times, clarity of information and explanations regarding procedures and treatments, staff behavior, the emergency department environment, and perceived quality of technical care—as well as patient-related factors, including age, gender, socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and illness severity.^{8,9} Factors such as cleanliness, the politeness of radiology staff, comfort during procedures like blood sampling, and the overall comfort of the waiting area are generally considered to have a lesser impact on patient satisfaction.^{10,11} A study done by Qayyum et al found that the majority of the respondents (77.2%) were satisfied with the emergency care they received.¹²

Development of newer tools and techniques to assess patient opinion is an emerging trend around the globe. This trend, however, has still not picked up in developing countries like

Pakistan, where most of the 'patient satisfaction studies' still focus on specific areas such as the emergency department. A study is thus required to survey patients' opinions of general aspects of inpatient care provided to them during admission. Such a study becomes even more important in light of the limited budget allocation to the health sector in Pakistan and the inability of many patients to afford expensive treatment modalities. Hence there is further need to prioritize spending and this study hopes to fill this void by production of data that can help managers and doctors to identify and address unsatisfactory factors in the care they provide.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Emergency Medicine, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi, from 2nd March 2025 to 2nd July 2025 following the approval of the research synopsis. A total of 189 patients were included in the study. The sample size was calculated using WHO software, based on a satisfaction prevalence of 77.2%, a 6% margin of error, and a 95% confidence level. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was employed for recruitment.

Patients aged between 20 and 80 years, of either gender, presenting to the emergency department were eligible for inclusion. Individuals were excluded if they had a recent emergency department visit, a history of a close family member's death in the emergency department, a hospitalization within the past three months, a diagnosis of malignancy or were undergoing chemotherapy, or had any known psychiatric illness.

Approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee and the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan. All participants were informed about the study's objectives, potential risks, and benefits. Written informed consent was obtained before enrollment. Each patient's level of satisfaction was assessed using a standardized questionnaire consisting of 16

questions. Patients were classified as "satisfied" if they answered "yes" to at least 12 questions and as "unsatisfied" if they responded "no" to 5 or more questions, based on the operational definitions.

Participants were monitored during their stay in the emergency department, and outcomes were recorded according to whether the patient was discharged home, transferred to a ward, or referred to another hospital. These outcomes were documented for both the satisfied and unsatisfied groups. All collected data were recorded using a structured proforma developed for the study.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20. For continuous variables such as age, the mean and standard deviation were calculated. If data were normally distributed, as determined by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, results were reported as mean \pm SD; otherwise, median and interquartile range (IQR) were used. Categorical variables such as gender, place of residence, income level, education status, employment status, satisfaction level, and patient outcomes were presented as frequencies and percentages.

To assess the influence of potential confounders, data were stratified by age, gender, place of residence, income, education, and occupation. Post-stratification analysis was carried out using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, where applicable. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 189 patients participated in the study. Of these, 108 (57.1%) were aged between 51 and 80 years, while 81 (42.9%) were between 20 and 50 years. Female participants comprised the majority (n=104; 55%), with males accounting for 85 (45%). Most respondents resided in urban areas (n=159; 84.1%), and the remaining 30 (15.9%) lived in rural settings.

In terms of occupational status, 115 (60.8%) of the patients were unemployed, and 74 (39.2%) reported being employed. Regarding household income, 103 (54.5%) reported a monthly

income exceeding 75,000 PKR, whereas 86 (45.5%) reported earnings at or below this threshold. Educational attainment varied, with 77 (40.7%) having received higher education, 62 (32.8%) completing secondary education, 39 (20.6%) attaining primary-level education, and 11 (5.9%) reporting no formal education.

When examining patient outcomes, the majority were transferred to inpatient wards (n=117; 61.9%), 63 (33.3%) were discharged home, and 9 (4.8%) were referred to other hospitals. In terms of overall satisfaction, 149 participants (78.8%) expressed satisfaction with the emergency department services, while 40 (21.2%) did not.

Table 2 presents patient satisfaction across demographic and clinical variables. Satisfaction levels did not differ significantly by age group (p=0.68), gender (p=0.72), place of residence (p=0.10), occupational status (p=0.80), income level (p=0.64), or education (p=0.21). However, satisfaction was marginally higher among rural residents (90%) compared to urban counterparts (76.7%), and patients with higher education levels reported greater satisfaction (85.7%) than those who were illiterate (63.6%). A statistically significant association emerged between patient outcome and satisfaction level (p=0.01). Among those who were admitted to the ward, 86.3% expressed satisfaction, compared to 63.5% of those who were discharged home. Patients who were referred to another facility also reported high satisfaction (88.9%). These findings suggest that continuity of care, reflected in admission or referral, may positively influence patient perceptions of emergency service quality.

DISCUSSION

The majority of patients reported being satisfied with the care they received, echoing findings from similar settings in Pakistan and elsewhere in South Asia.¹³⁻¹⁵ These results contribute to the growing body of literature that emphasizes the importance of patient-centered care, even in high-pressure environments such as emergency departments.

Notably, satisfaction levels did not differ significantly by age, gender, education, employment status, or monthly income. These findings are consistent with earlier research from Saudi Arabia and Bangladesh, where similar studies observed weak or inconsistent associations between sociodemographic characteristics and satisfaction.^{13, 15-16} Although these variables did not reach statistical significance in our study, we observed some notable trends. For instance, rural patients expressed higher satisfaction than urban residents. This may reflect differences in expectations or previous experiences with healthcare services, as suggested in earlier research.^{13, 16}

Among all variables assessed, patient outcome showed the strongest association with satisfaction. Patients who were admitted or referred to another facility expressed significantly greater satisfaction compared to those discharged home. These findings align with earlier studies that identified perceived thoroughness and continuity of care as key factors influencing satisfaction in emergency settings.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Patients who are sent home may feel that their condition was not fully addressed, especially if the communication during discharge was unclear or rushed.

The role of waiting time also emerged as important. While our study did not find a statistically significant association between waiting time and satisfaction, many patients still expressed dissatisfaction with delays in receiving care. This is consistent with prior evidence that perceived waiting time. This is regardless of the actual duration, and often influenced satisfaction.¹⁷⁻¹⁸ Improving triage efficiency and communicating expected wait times could help address this concern.

Our findings also underscore the value of effective provider-patient communication. Several earlier studies have shown that patients who receive clear explanations, feel listened to, and perceive respectful treatment are more likely to report satisfaction, regardless of the clinical outcome.^{13-14, 18} Although our study did not include direct questions about provider

communication, the observed trends suggest that attention to interpersonal aspects of care could further improve patient experience.

Interestingly, education did not significantly predict satisfaction, although patients with higher education levels tended to report greater satisfaction. This observation contrasts with some international findings. In those studies where lower education was associated with higher satisfaction, often attributed to lower expectations.^{16, 19} In our setting, the more educated patients may have better understood the care process. This in turn could have increased their comfort and trust in the system. While we did not specifically measure language barriers or the availability of interpreter services, other studies have identified these as important contributors to satisfaction, particularly in multilingual and multicultural urban settings.^{18, 20} In Karachi's diverse population, incorporating culturally competent communication strategies and interpreter support may be worth exploring in future interventions.

Overall, this study highlights several actionable areas to improve patient satisfaction in emergency care. Thus ensuring timely and efficient triage, enhancing provider-patient communication, and improving discharge processes. These findings support the broader global push toward patient-centered emergency care and align with strategies recommended in previous research on ED service delivery and quality.²¹⁻²²

LIMITATIONS

This study took place in a single tertiary care hospital, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other settings. We also did not assess factors such as illness severity or provider communication, which could have influenced patient satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

We found that most patients were satisfied with the care they received in the emergency department, and that their satisfaction was closely linked to the outcome of their visit.

Patients who were admitted or referred expressed greater satisfaction than those discharged home. Demographic characteristics did not show a strong association with satisfaction. However, our findings highlight

the need to strengthen discharge communication, ensure continuity of care, and focus on patient experience as a core component of emergency service delivery.

Table 1: Distribution of baseline characteristics among the study participants.

Variables	n (%)
Age	
20 to 50 years	81 (42.9)
51 to 80 years	108 (57.1)
Gender	
Male	85 (45)
Female	104 (55)
Place of residence	
Urban	159 (84.1)
Rural	30 (15.9)
Occupational status	
Employed	74 (39.2)
Unemployed	115 (60.8)
Family monthly income	
≤75000 per month	86 (45.5)
>75000 per month	103 (54.5)
Educational status	
Illiterate	11 (5.9)
Primary	39 (20.6)
Secondary	62 (32.8)
Higher	77 (40.7)
Patient outcome	
Patient sent home	63 (33.3)
Patient transferred to ward	117 (61.9)
Patient referred to other hospital	09 (4.8)
Level of patient satisfaction	
Satisfied	149 (78.8)
Unsatisfied	40 (21.2)
Total	189 (100)

Table 2: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the Level of patient satisfaction.

Variables	Satisfied n (%)	Unsatisfied n (%)	P value
Age 20 to 50 years 51 to 80 years	65 (80.2) 84 (77.8)	16 (19.8) 24 (22.2)	0.68
Gender Male Female	68 (80) 81 (77.9)	17 (20) 23 (22.1)	0.72
Place of residence Urban Rural	122 (76.7) 27 (90)	37 (23.3) 03 (10)	0.10
Occupational status Employed Unemployed	59 (79.7) 90 (78.3)	15 (20.3) 25 (21.7)	0.80
Family monthly income ≤75000 per month >75000 per month	73 (84.9) 76 (73.8)	13 (15.1) 27 (26.2)	0.64
Educational status Illiterate Primary Secondary Higher	07 (63.6) 29 (74.4) 47 (75.8) 66 (85.7)	04 (36.4) 10 (25.6) 15 (24.2) 11 (14.3)	0.21
Patient outcome Patient sent home Patient transferred to ward Patient referred to other hospital	40 (63.5) 101 (86.3) 08 (88.9)	23 (36.5) 16 (13.7) 01 (11.1)	0.01

Figure 1: Distribution of patient satisfaction rates across demographic and clinical outcome categories among individuals presenting to a tertiary care emergency department in Karachi (n = 189).

Patients who were admitted to inpatient wards or referred to other hospitals reported the highest satisfaction levels, while those discharged home showed lower satisfaction. Rural participants and those with higher education tended to report greater satisfaction, although these differences did not reach statistical significance. The figure illustrates how outcome of care influenced satisfaction more strongly than demographic characteristics.

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